

Sheath rot symptoms (arrow) produced from spray inoculation of a spore suspension in 25% beef extract-peptone solution on carborundum-treated plants. IRRI, 1980.

appeared 2 weeks after inoculation and became progressively severe with time (see photo).

Wounding of the plants with carborundum before inoculation greatly increased disease development (see

table). Plants not treated with carborundum remained disease-free; however, those sprayed with 50% beef extract-peptone amendment registered minimal infection (16.6% infected plants). ■

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at LPPM, Indonesia

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The life span and tungro transmission ability of *Nephotettix virescens*, collected and reared locally, were tested on seed-

lings of 10 rice varieties at LPPM Indonesia, from 20 October to 25 December 1978. There were two trials which involved 800 adult insects — 40 females and 40 males for each variety. After an acquisition access time of 4 days on tungro-diseased plants, the insects survived 1 to 25 days. The average life span was 5.6 days (6.1 days for female insects and 5.1 days for the male).

Considering the average life span of

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the insect, rice varieties Ptb 18, IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Pankhari 203 appeared more resistant than the other varieties in the test (see table).

Twelve percent of 2,803 seedlings inoculated by the insects became infected. The insects showed low efficiency in transmitting the tungro virus to Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, Kataribhog, Ptb 18, and IR34. Those varieties appeared more resistant to tungro than the others in the test. ■

Life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at LPPM, Indonesia, in 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Longest	Av ^a		Longest	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Kataribhog	25	7.7 a	26	2	1.1	7	0.28	1.05
TN1	23	7.6 a	73	4	1.4	25	0.96	1.33
Latisail	21	7.3 a	56	2	1.2	15	0.61	1.09
IR26	14	7.1 a	64	4	1.5	22	0.84	1.31
Ambemohar 159	16	6.5 a	43	2	1.1	11	0.46	1.09
Habiganj DW8	22	6.4 a	14	1	1.0	4	0.14	1.00
Pankhari 203	15	4.2 b	6	2	1.4	2	0.06	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	13	3.7 b	46	2	1.1	16	0.49	1.05
IR 34	10	3.1 b	23	1	1.0	10	0.29	1.05
Ptb 18	6	2.4 c	23	1	1.0	10	0.23	1.00
Max or av	25	5.6	38	4	1.2	12	0.44	1.10

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.